

**RATIONAL NUTRITION IN THE LIFE OF STUDENTS
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Аннотация. В статье показана роль рационального питания в жизни студентов. Рассмотрены его принципы и основы, правильная организация меню и благотворное влияние на здоровье. А также нормы рационального питания для студентов.

Abstract. The article shows the role of rational nutrition in the life of students. Its principles and bases, proper menu organization and beneficial effect on health are considered. As well as the norms of rational nutrition for students.

Ключевые слова: питание, студенты, жизнь, здоровье, человек.

Key words: food, students, life, health, person.

Relevance: Most people eat incorrectly. Many people do not know how to create a balanced diet. It is important that every person knows how to eat rationally, as this plays one of the main roles in a healthy lifestyle.

Research on rational nutrition of modern youth

A balanced diet is an important factor in a healthy lifestyle. This is why it is so important to understand the basics and principles of nutrition.

Tasks:

1. Assess youth involvement in proper nutrition;
2. Determine the impact of nutrition on youth;
3. Research the most popular food among young people;
4. Find out why young people eat properly.

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The object of the study is students of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution "VGSPU".

The subject of the study is the influence of proper nutrition on the lives of young people. Research results:

When conducting a study on the topic "Rational nutrition in the lives of young people," 98 people were interviewed, of which 28% were boys and 72% were girls.

Of all respondents, they knew about the basics and principles of proper nutrition 15.8%, and 84.2% did not know.

Fig.1. Students who know about nutrition principles

Students who have knowledge of healthy nutrition standards do not plan to learn new information. People who do not know the principles of proper nutrition would be happy to study this topic at a deeper level.

Fig. 2. Desire to study this topic 146/164

Most respondents do not know how to prepare a balanced diet. Students who know the basics and principles of proper nutrition can easily create a menu, both for themselves and for others. And some of those students who cannot create a menu themselves will turn to a specialist.

Fig.3. Students who know how to prepare a balanced diet

Table 1

AVERAGE DAILY SET OF PRODUCTS FOR STUDENTS

Products	Quantity in grams	Products	Quantity in grams
Rye bread	250	Fruits, fresh	50
Wheat bread		juices	
Egg	150	Cereals,	
Fish	36	legumes	60
Meat, offal	64	Sugar,	95
Vegetables	240	confectionery	
Potatoes	340	Dried fruits	16
Cottage cheese	320	Water	
Cheese	24	Tea	1000
Sour cream	15	Flour	200
		Rusks	20
		Vegetable oil	5
		Animal fats	22

In total, there are three principles of rational nutrition, the first of which includes energy balance, the energy value of the daily diet must correspond to

the energy expenditure of the body. On average, they amount to 2000 kcal for mental work, and for physical work up to 4000 kcal per day.

The second principle is a balanced diet, I agree that it is necessary to consume the exact ratio of proteins, fats and carbohydrates.

Protein – 1g of protein per 1 kg of weight, half of this amount should be of plant origin and half of animal origin. The amount of fat should be 15-30% of calories.

The best ratio is considered to be 3-7% polyunsaturated fatty acids, 7-10% calories from saturated fatty acids and 10-15% from monounsaturated fatty acids. Carbohydrates should make up 55-75% of daily calories, of which 5-10% is allocated to simple carbohydrates such as sugar, and the rest to complex carbohydrates.

The third principle is the diet, 3-4 meals are considered the most favorable. Meals should be regular and even, no later than 2-3 hours before bedtime.

Basic rules of rational nutrition:

- 1) Accounting for the composition of food products;
- 2) Adequate intake of water and nutrients;
- 3) Equality of calories in a person's daily diet and energy expenditure;
- 4) Add dietary fiber to your diet;
- 5) Varied menu;
- 6) Power mode.

At the moment, most students do not know about proper and balanced nutrition, but many of them strive to gain this knowledge. Those who possess them actively use them in everyday life and are happy to help others. Consequently, many strive for a healthy lifestyle.

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